

Branded EC Zenodo-community design (D2.1)

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Introduction

A specific objective of HORIZON-ZEN is to develop an enhanced Zenodo-community named “EU Open Research” (EOR-community) for the EU’s research programme beneficiaries. Following is a short report illustrating the agreed branding for the EOR-community.

Name of the community

The current name of the Zenodo-community “EU Open Research” has high similarity with the “Open Research Europe”¹ open access publishing platform. To avoid confusion among programme beneficiaries we suggest to rename the community to one of the following names:

- Open Repository
- Open Research Repository
- Open Science
- Open Science Repository
- Projects Repository
- Research Commons
- Research Exchange
- Research Hub
- EU Funded Research
- EU Open Repository
- EU Open Research Repository
- EU Open Science
- EU Open Science Repository
- EU Projects Repository
- EU Repository
- EU Research
- EU Research Commons
- EU Research Community
- EU Research Exchange
- EU Research Hub

¹ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

Design

Community frontpage

The EOR-community will be accessible on the URL <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu>. On the URL, a user will be presented with the following page.

Header and footer

The header and footer will clearly show the EC's visual identity by using the logo and colors of the EC as shown in the mockup.

The footer will contain links to text pages relevant to the community. The current menu is only an example of potential pages.

Menu

The community has a standard Zenodo-community menu with the following links:

- Search - links to *Search* page (see mockup below)
- Browse- links to *Browse* page (see mockup below)
- Metrics - Out of scope. Intention is to eventually link to a dashboard showing metrics for the community (usage statistics, content statistics, etc).
- Curation policy - links to a text page explaining the curation policy for the community
- About - links to a text page about the community.

Modules

The page has been made in a modular fashion (i.e. all modules can be reordered if desired), consisting of the following modules:

- **Branding/slogan and key actions**
 - A key message and call to action for “New upload” and “Request a community”
- **Announcements**
 - A list of announcements specific to the community. The mockup shows potential examples.
- **Featured project community**
 - Prominently feature project communities (e.g. a new one each day) based on criteria
- **Browse**
 - Ability to get a quick overview over content in the EOR-community enabling to browse by subject area, funding programme, or for one of the project communities
- **Recent/popular uploads**

- The module will allow showing recent uploads that were accepted into the EOR-community, and popular uploads (e.g. most viewed record in the past week).
- **How it works?**
 - Explains the key concept for the EOR-community to help users understand what they need to do in order to participate.

EU Open Research

https://www.zenodo.org/communities/eu

zenodo Search Communities My dashboard lars.holmnielsen

European Commission | EU Projects Repository

Research and Innovation

Search Browse Metrics Curation policy About

FAIR publishing made simple
Publish your research outputs FAIR with EU Projects Repository.

+ New upload Request community Learn more

Announcements See all

Aug 23, 2024 Meets us at EOSC Symposium 2024
Jun 7, 2024 Call for early adopters for our project-spaces
Feb 15, 2024 European Commission launches new community on Zenodo to improve FAIR research publishing

Featured community

ACCESS
Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable, safe and flexible CCUS

View

5 publications 20 datasets 1k views 50 members

Browse

Subject areas

- Social sciences
- Natural sciences
- HE Engineering and technology
- Humanities
- Agricultural sciences
- Medical and health sciences

Browse all

Indexed communities

Recent My communities Filter

HIPPOCRATES - Health Initiatives in Psoriasis and Psoriatic arthritis ConsorTium European States
2021-2026

ZeroW - Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain
2022-2025

ACCESS - Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable, safe and flexible CCUS
2021-2025

See all

Funding programmes

- COST Actions
- Euroatom
- HE Horizon Europe
- Horizon 2020
- European Research Council (ERC)
- Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions

Browse all

Recent uploads | Popular uploads

Jan 31, 2023 (1.0.0) Dataset Open access

M100 dataset 11: 22-08

Andrea Borghesi, Carmine Di Santi, Martin Malari, Mohean Seyedkazemi Ardebili, Alessio Mauri

Published in [REGALE, EUPEX, The European Pilot, DECICE, Graph-MaskWizer](#)

51 5

Jan 31, 2023 (1.0.0) Dataset Open access

Forward-modelled reflectance from spring and summer Baltic Sea specific inherent optical properties

Simis, Stefan G.H., Yildatola, Pasi, Kallio, Kari, Spilling, Kristian, Kutser, Tiit

Published in [DEVOTES, JERICO, PROTOOL, COBIO5, WATERS](#)

121 125

Jun 30, 2023 Deliverable Open access

CRAFT-OA Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

Arasteh-Roodary, Sona Lisa, Holsinger, Sy, Klaus, Tabaei, Poasovec, Kristina

Published in [CRAFT-OA](#)

1 1

How it works?

1. Request community 2. Invite partners 3. Publish FAIR

Learn more

Managed by European Commission
Contact openscience@ec.europa.eu

About How it works? FAQ Contact

FAIR publishing Submit your research

Integrations REST API OAI-PMH FAIR evaluation tools

Powered by CERN Data Centre & InvenioRDM Verified community - Learn more? Status Privacy policy Terms of use Support

Browse

The browse page is accessed from the “Browse” community menu item. The goal of the page is to provide an overview of what content exists in the community.

EU Open Research

zenodo Search Communities My dashboard lars.holm.nielsen

European Commission EU Projects Repository + New upload Request community

Research and Innovation Search Browse Metrics Curation policy About

Summary

10.189 projects 500.000 records 300 TB data volume

Funding programmes

COST Actions 10,123 Euroatom 523 HE Horizon Europe 2,928 H2020 Horizon 2020 98,230 Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions 10,123 ERC European Research Council (ERC) 302

Subjects

Social sciences 10,123 Natural sciences 523 HE Engineering and technology 2,928 H2020 Humanities 98,230

[Economics and business](#)
[Educational sciences](#)
[Law](#)
[Media and communications](#)
[Political sciences](#)
[Psychology](#)
[Social geography](#)
[Sociology](#)
[Other social sciences](#)

[Earth And Related Environmental Sciences](#)
[Mathematics](#)
[Biological Sciences](#)
[Chemical Sciences](#)
[Physical Sciences](#)
[Computer And Information Sciences](#)
[Other Natural Sciences](#)

[Chemical Engineering](#)
[Civil Engineering](#)
[Electrical Engineering, Electronic](#)
[Engineering, Information Engineering](#)
[Environmental Biotechnology](#)
[Environmental Engineering](#)
[Industrial Biotechnology](#)
[Materials Engineering](#)
[Mechanical Engineering](#)
[Medical Engineering](#)
[Nanotechnology](#)
[Other Engineering And Technologies](#)

[Arts](#)
[History And Archaeology](#)
[Languages And Literature](#)
[Philosophy, Ethics And Religion](#)
[Other Humanities](#)

Agricultural sciences 10,123 Medical and health sciences 302

[Agricultural Sciences](#)
[Agriculture, Forestry, And Fisheries](#)
[Animal And Dairy Science](#)
[Veterinary Sciences](#)
[Other Agricultural Sciences](#)

[Basic Medicine](#)
[Clinical Medicine](#)
[Health Sciences](#)
[Medical Biotechnology](#)
[Other Medical Sciences](#)

Indexed communities 1021

The EU Projects Repository is indexing records from 1021 project communities.

See all

Managed by European Commission
Contact: openscience@ec.europa.eu

About: How it works?, FAQ, Contact

FAIR publishing: Getting started, Submit your research

Integrations: REST API, OAI-PMH, FAIR evaluation tools

Powered by CERN Data Centre & InvenioRDM Verified community - Learn more? Status Privacy policy Terms of use Support

Summary

The summary will display some key numbers about content in the community such as number of records, number of communities, and total data volume to enable users to get a sense of how much content is in the community.

Collections: Funding programmes/Subject areas

Both “funding programme” and “subjects” sections are collections that support up to a 2-level hierarchy. A collection is defined as a query over all content in the community (e.g. Horizon 2020 could be defined as a query over all records linked to a H2020 grant).

European Science Vocabulary

The subject areas will use the European Science Vocabulary² (EuroSciVoc) published by the EU Publications Office and used by CORDIS to classify content.

Browse: View/search collection

From the *Browse* page, a user can access an individual collection - e.g. the Funding Programmes > Horizon 2020 collection.

The search bar allows contextualised search in:

- The specific collection (e.g. search only records in Horizon 2020 collection)
- The full EOR-community.
- All of Zenodo.

A collection will have a logo/description.

The facets can be customised for each collection (chosen among a set of possible facets).

Browse: Project communities

From the *Browse* page and from the *Community frontpage*, a user can access a page to search and browse project communities.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface for browsing project communities. The browser address bar displays <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/eu/p/verify>. The Zenodo logo and navigation menu are at the top. The main content area is titled "Indexed communities" with a count of 1021. A search bar and a "Sort" dropdown are present. On the left, there are filter sections for "Funding programme", "Subjects", "Organisations", and "Application domain". The main table lists communities, with the first entry being "eosc FAIR-EASE FAIR-EASE - FAIR Earth Sciences & Environment services" under the "Horizon Europe" funding programme, dated "2021-2025" with 121 items. A "+ New upload" button is located to the right of the first row. The footer contains contact information, links for "About", "FAIR publishing", and "Integrations", and a "Verified community" badge.

Search

The search page is accessed from the “Search” menu item, or alternatively simply by the user searching in the community.

The search bar is contextualised to allow search in only the EOR-community or in all of Zenodo.

A search result item (i.e. a single record) will be adapted to the EC colours, but otherwise display the same information as search results on all of Zenodo.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo search interface for the 'EU Open Research' community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation tabs for 'Search', 'Browse', 'Insights', 'Curation policy', and 'About'. The search results are sorted by 'Most recent'. On the left, there are filter sections for 'Versions', 'Access status', 'Resource type', 'Subjects', and 'Project'. The main content area shows three search results:

- M100 dataset 11: 22-08**: A dataset uploaded on Jan 31, 2023, with open access. It is part of a larger data set collected from the most recent Tier-0 supercomputer hosted at CINECA (Marconi100).
- Forward-modelled reflectance from spring and summer Baltic Sea specific inherent optical properties**: A dataset uploaded on Jan 31, 2023, with open access. It is an extensive dataset of remote-sensing reflectance (Rrs, units sr-1) spectra based on forward modelling of mean concentration-specific inherent optical properties (SIOPs).
- CRAFT-OA Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan**: A deliverable uploaded on Jun 30, 2023, with open access. It outlines the overall communication and dissemination plan (CDP) for the CRAFT-OA project.

The footer contains information about the community being managed by the European Commission, contact details (opscience@ec.europa.eu), and funding by the European Union.

Request project community

The request community page can be accessed via the “Request community” button in the header and frontpage. The purpose of the page is to enable a project coordinator to get a subcommunity for their EC-funded project.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://www.zenodo.org/communities/eu>. The page is titled "EU Projects Repository" and features a navigation bar with "Search", "Browse", "Communities", "Insights", "Curation policy", and "About". A "Request community" button is visible in the top right. The main content area is titled "Setup new community for EU-funded project" and contains the following form fields:

- Community:** A question "Do you already have an existing community on Zenodo for your EU-funded project?" with radio buttons for "Yes" and "No".
- Project:** A text input field labeled "Search for project".
- Community name:** A text input field containing "VERIFY".
- Identifier:** A text input field containing "eu.verify".
- Subject areas:** An empty text input field.
- Organisations:** An empty text input field.

A green "+ Create community" button is located at the bottom of the form. The footer includes contact information for the European Commission, links for "About", "FAIR publishing", and "Integrations", and a footer bar with "Powered by CERN Data Centre & InvenioRDM", "Verified community - Learn more?", and "Status Privacy policy Terms of use Support".

Existing or new

The page will allow linking an existing community already created on Zenodo into the EOR-community, or it will create a new community for the project coordinator.

Project link

A project coordinator will be required to link the project community to a project in CORDIS. This enables us to automatically discover subject areas and organisations from the CORDIS database.

Project Community Frontpage

A project community is simply another Zenodo-community for an EC-funded project which is linked to the EOR-community. This means that all records in the project community are automatically indexed in the EOR-community. Also e.g. curation checks from the EOR-community are inherited by the project community.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo Project Community Frontpage for the 'VERIFY' project. The page is titled 'VERIFY - Observation-based system for monitoring and verification of greenhouse gases' and is identified as a 'verified EU project community'. The header includes the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The main content area features a search bar with a dropdown menu showing 'craft-aa' results, both 'In this community' and 'In EU Projects Repository'. Below this is a 'Browse' section with filters for 'Publications' (6), 'Datasets' (5), 'HE Project deliverables' (12), and 'Presentations' (12). A 'Browse all' link is provided. The 'Recent uploads' section displays three items: 'M100 dataset 11: 22-08', 'Forward-modelled reflectance from spring and summer Baltic Sea specific inherent optical properties', and 'CRAFT-OA Deliverable 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan'. Each item includes a date, type, open access status, authors, and publication information. A 'How it works?' section follows, with three steps: '1. Request community', '2. Invite partners', and '3. Publish FAIR', accompanied by a 'Learn more' button. The footer contains the European Commission logo, 'EU Projects Repository' branding, and links for 'About', 'FAIR publishing', and 'Integrations'. The page is powered by CERN Data Centre & InvenioRDM and is a verified community.

Header/footer

The header and footer of the project community will be styled similarly to the EOR-community but with the project's logo in the header, and with a clear link to the EOR-community in the footer.

Record landing pages

A record submitted to a project community will also be rendered with the project community's branding:

The screenshot shows a Zenodo record landing page for the 'VERIFY' community. The page is titled 'The Global Carbon Project's fossil CO2 emissions dataset' and is published on 17 October, 2022, as Version 2. The authors listed are Andrew, Robbie M. and Peters, Glen P. The citation provided is: M. Andrew, R., & P. Peters, G. (2022). The Global Carbon Project's fossil CO2 emissions dataset. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215364>. The description states that the Global Carbon Project (GCP) has been publishing estimates of global and national fossil CO2 emissions since 2001, and that the dataset includes both standard, absolute form, and per capita, with associated metadata files in JSON format. The 'Files' section lists four files: 'MCO2_fit.csv' (3.0 MB), 'MCO2_fit_metadata.json' (3.6 kB), 'percapita_fit.csv' (2.6 MB), and 'percapita_fit_metadata.json' (3.2 kB). The 'Metrics' section shows 28,089 views and 52,260 downloads. The 'Versions' section shows two versions: Version v2 (17 Oct, 2022) and Version v1 (14 Oct, 2021). The 'Details' section includes the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3594204, keywords 'Fossil CO2 emissions', 'Global Carbon Project', 'Carbon emissions', and 'Carbon dioxide', and the resource type 'Dataset'. The 'Rights' section shows Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. The 'Export' section has a dropdown menu set to 'JSON' and an 'Export' button. The footer includes the European Commission logo, 'EU Projects Repository', and contact information.